

BIOPLATFORMS
AUSTRALIA

Australian
BioCommons

Australian BioCommons

Strategic Plan

2019-2023

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Additional Information

Further information about the Australian BioCommons can be found at <https://www.biocommons.org.au/>

1. Executive Summary

Digital technologies are proving transformational for the life sciences. The Australian Bioinformatics Commons (BioCommons) is an ambitious new digital capability that will enhance Australian research in its ability to understand the molecular basis of life across environmental, agricultural and biomedical science. The investment in the BioCommons will ensure Australian life science research remains globally competitive, by providing access to the digital tools, methods and training researchers require, in order to respond to national challenges such as food security, environmental conservation and disease treatments.

The BioCommons will deliver new capabilities for the estimated thirty thousand publicly funded bioscience researchers in Australia.

- It will enhance coordination in the planning and development of research infrastructure supporting bioinformatics in bioscience research; and
 - Provide leadership through the development of the BioCommons;
 - Distil community agreement around infrastructure requirements;
 - Develop an enhanced engagement with e-infrastructure providers to meet those requirements;
 - Foster the supply and use of infrastructure and related access policies tuned for bioinformatics work practices; and
 - Continue and strengthen the existing deep engagement with our peers in international jurisdictions, particularly Europe and the USA.
- It will invest in general capabilities that improve the ability of many of Australia's best researchers to more easily undertake leading edge bioinformatics analyses. These capabilities will be applicable across all areas of life science research. Founding elements of the general capabilities include:
 - A continuously improved and expanded Galaxy Australia service;
 - A continuously improved and expanded Framework Data Portal; and
 - A new enhanced workflow, analysis, data access and portability capability for life science research built into national and institutional e-infrastructures.
- It will also invest in specialist capabilities that address well characterised and high priority challenges in specific domains of life science research.

The BioCommons will engage technology partners to enable access to these capabilities via a cloud infrastructure termed the 'BioCloud'. The 'BioCloud' is envisaged as the harmonised delivery of e-infrastructure capabilities to life science research, composed from national e-infrastructure (NCRIS funded) entities, institutional and institution funded cooperative entities and commercial suppliers.

Overall the BioCommons will be delivered in partnership with a network of Australian and global bioinformatics and data intensive research groups and will ensure Australian researchers can interpret increasingly complex outputs derived from Australia's investments in genome sequencing, proteomic and metabolic platforms.

2. The BioCommons

2.1 Mission

Digital technologies are proving transformational for the life sciences. This investment in digital infrastructure ensures Australian life science research remains globally competitive and that Australian researchers will have access to the tools, methods and training they require to respond to national challenges such as food security, environmental conservation and disease treatments.

It is the mission of the BioCommons to:

- Sustain strategic leadership in the provision and use of bioinformatics and bioscience data infrastructures at a national scale
- Actively support life science research communities with community scale digital infrastructure
- Provide access to services that:
 - Provide sophisticated analysis capabilities, including software and hardware platforms that underpin world class science, especially where developed and maintained in concert with international peer infrastructures
 - Support digital asset stewardship and management, retention, integration and publication solutions as they evolve
 - Enable researchers to observe best-practice data standards, management, interoperability and publication approaches as they evolve
- Provide enduring access to the digital methods, data and tools, that are needed by world class environmental, agricultural and biomedical research.
- Provide training and support solutions that enable the rapid and broad based adoption of the above

2.2 Core Functions

The BioCommons will comprise three components:

- BioCommons Hub - providing governance, leadership, planning and management
- BioCommons Services - providing the services and functionality
- BioCommons Cloud - providing the necessary compute infrastructure capacity

The BioCommons Hub will scale slowly as the BioCommons expands whereas the BioCommons Services and the BioCommons Cloud itself can be expected to grow significantly in complexity and in budget commitment over the next five years and beyond.

2.3 Principles

National and international consultations have informed the following core principles.

1. Govern through a national focus on capabilities and communities
2. Partner internationally: participate in and contribute to larger critical mass efforts where possible; reuse and improve rather than build anew
3. Build a software and expertise capability that will reduce duplication of infrastructure management in Australia and allow efforts to be re-focussed on methods development and dissemination
4. Promote the development of, and build on, high throughput cloud infrastructure that is interoperable with international (initially US and European) equivalents, using established, well supported software platforms
5. Streamline the exchange of tools, workflows, data and training both nationally and internationally and support workforce development as much as possible

2.4 Lead In

The BioCommons builds on many years of investment by both [Bioplatforms Australia](#) (BPA) and the forerunners to the [Australian Research Data Commons](#) (ARDC). A pathfinder project between BPA, ARDC and Australia's research network provider [AARNet](#) built towards the BioCommons through an initial set of prioritised activities. The project grew significantly with the participation of the Australia research authentication provider, the [AAF](#), and Australia's two peak computing facilities, [NCI](#) and [Pawsey](#). Four year funding for the BioCommons proper was committed by the board of BPA in April 2019.

Figure 1: Staged Development of the Australian BioCommons

3. Implementation

The BioCommons will support 'omic data enabled research in the domains of Agriculture, Biodiversity and Human Health. It will be shaped by a unified leadership and will operate across as common an infrastructure as is possible. The way the BioCommons is used is expected to have a significantly different emphasis in the three domains.

The intention is to enhance research productivity and capability by:

- Providing the software, services and reference/shared data used by biologists,
- While absorbing the complexity of the corresponding digital services, systems and e-infrastructure capabilities in use at any time.

The explosion in 'omic data volumes is driving innovation in new technologies that extract knowledge from the data and support the use of distributed data resources. Fundamentally, the needs of data intense biology, considering both the volumes of data and the number of research users, do challenge the scale of available research sector hosted infrastructure. At the same time relevant skills and investment exist in the commercial sector where the ability to support large data and large user cohorts is driven by the largest scales of both. Leading bioscience institutions in the US and Europe, are reporting real benefits from a 'cloud first' approach and institutions in the US in particular are increasingly entering into strategic relationships with commercial cloud providers for underpinning e-infrastructure.

Many of the infrastructure challenges confronting biology are being addressed cooperatively and internationally and Australia must join such initiatives. It is important to free up research resources to meet our challenges in line with international efforts.

The BioCommons is structured to respond to this context through three components that layer its connectivity to stakeholders, international leadership in functionality and the best available supply of local infrastructure capability and capacity.

3.1 BioCommons Hub

3.1.1 Governance, Leadership and Community Engagement

The development of a BioCommons enduring into the foreseeable future is a complex undertaking requiring purpose specific leadership and governance. Its success will hinge on community engagement. The leadership function will need to deliver:

- An Australian presence with a national voice
- All necessary plans, prioritisation decisions and agreements
- All required policies including financial arrangements
- A clear legal representation for action
- An Australian point of engagement for global activities
- Agreements between participants implementing the above

A board outline of the organisational structure is depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The overall structure of the BioCommons

While shown here as three distinct layers it is envisaged that some services will be very closely related to the provisioning of infrastructure.

Achieving a differentiated use of the BioCommons, to support different research activities, while also achieving international conformity in the supply of the BioCommons Cloud, will be critical to the optimum outcomes for Australian research.

3.1.2 Community Engagement and Pathfinding

The concept of pathfinding provides a valuable framework for the steps through which services need to progress. The concept is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: The community focussed pathfinding process

Developments in technologies, instruments, data and methods continuously appearing on the horizon in 'omics imply a real need for continuous pathfinding.

The pathfinding process will:

- Be the proving ground for functionality enhancements for the BioCommons;
- Engage internationally in the exploration and evaluations of new technologies and solutions; and
- Provide implementation advice proven through practical local realisation

3.2 BioCommons Services

The BioCommons Services will provide access to reference data, software and services that enhance the productivity and capability of Australian research biologists and research bioinformaticians. It will do so across a range of scales of bioinformatics intensity. An associated BioCommons Cloud will ensure that the effective use of those services is possible, a challenge in itself considering the number of researchers involved.

Important target elements of the BioCommons Services can be identified as set out in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Prospective elements of the BioCommons Services

The BioCommons Services will:

- Realise agreed technical and service functionality to ensure world's best practice in digital data and methods is available to Australian biological research;
- Support the majority of Australian biologists through provision of high performance standard informatics methods, as well as supporting the specialised needs of very intensive bioinformatics enabled science;
- Deliver day to day management and user support for the BioCommons Services;
- Roll-out BioCommons functionalities (when deemed appropriate) that emerge from pathfinding activities;
- Develop and supply training and support for biologists and bioinformaticians; and
- Implement appropriate BioCommons participation arrangements.

3.3 BioCommons Cloud

The BioCommons Cloud will provide the digital services, systems and e-infrastructure required to support the BioCommons Services as used by Australia’s research biologists and research bioinformaticians.

This is one of the most challenging aspects of the BioCommons given the scale of the data and the number of researchers expected to be involved. The BioCommons Cloud is expected to require the use of substantial on-premise high throughput cloud infrastructure and substantial use of commercial clouds. Because most important international life science data collections will be off-shore, the BioCommons Cloud must engage internationally.

The BioCommons Cloud will:

- Access and/or provide capacity and capability in support of the BioCommons, mixing on-premise and commercial supply to best advantage;
- Deliver day to day management and user support for the BioCommons Cloud providing a high level cloud capability that biologists and bioinformaticians can reliably build on;
- Roll-out BioCommons Cloud functionality emerging from the pathfinder component; and
- Implement appropriate BioCommons Cloud participation arrangements.

4. Governance Goals

4.1 Participation

The overall scale of the BioCommons will be driven by participation in the capabilities it provides.

The Biocommons will be progressed by:

- A BPA provided investment into the BioCommons Services layer accessing features

and functionality provided through many national research infrastructures;

- The construction of a BioCommons Cloud infrastructure underpinning the BioCommons Services, developed with the support of the AAF, AARNet, ARDC, NCI and Pawsey; and
- The expansion of the BioCommons into a leading national research asset with the participation of Universities, Medical Research Institutes, Publicly Funded Research Agencies and other government agencies, applying the BioCommons in the areas of Agriculture, BioDiversity and Human Health.

In broad terms the investment from BPA is scaled at \$20M over the four financial years from 2019 to 2023. The resources supplied to the research community through the BioCommons Services and Cloud infrastructure, including from institutions, the AAF, AARNet, the ARDC, NCI and Pawsey, is expected to more than double that amount.

In addition, the BioCommons Cloud will be an ideal residence for 'omics data once it is created and curated, and for 'omic reference data assets held for the long term. The combining of new data with such reference data is a fundamental requirement of 'omics enabled research. Therefore the ultimate success of the BioCommons will arise when Institutions choose to support their researchers to grow reference data sets through the BioCommons Services and the BioCommons Cloud. In that scenario the expectation on the resource budget in future years would be much higher than that given above.

Achieving a 'build in the commons' approach from significant bioscience research institutions is a key performance indicator for the success of the BioCommons.

4.2 Focus

The BioCommons will combine technical and human resources from across Australia to address the challenges confronting digital data intense life science research. Addressing those challenges will enhance the efficiency, effectiveness, competitiveness and capability of future Australian biological research, and its translation into research impact.

The challenges prioritised in consultation to date, together with the planned BioCommons response, are set out in Figure 4. Prioritised core capabilities are expected to include:

- A service to which a researcher brings their research goals, tools, pipelines and data, that seamlessly integrates with all the resources they might need;
- A compute and data intensive infrastructure for the advancement of bioinformatics research and bioinformatics intensive biological research;
- A means by which datasets can be integrated by collaborators across institutions; and
- A means by which omics data can be included in the broader data integrations occurring in research translation and in research applications.

Challenge	Planned BioCommons Response
'Omics Data	
The simple retention and preservation of data at the volumes expected.	Integration of relevant controlled access data services in the BioCommons, scaled by data owners or stewards growing the BioCommons Cloud to the requisite storage capacity.
The curation of data at the scale and complexity envisaged.	Provision of collaboration platforms supporting tools and workflows that enable best practice curation, available to all bioscience communities.
The onshore use of large offshore sources of primary reference data.	Pathfinding with international efforts to develop more effective approaches, to be deployed when ready into the BioCommons Cloud and to be available to all BioCommons Services.
The research use of large clinical and other non-research genomic collections.	BioCommons leadership negotiating the means for research access to such data sets, to be delivered through an agreed BioCommons interface.
'Omics Methods	
The ability to find, connect and co-analyse independently held and managed data.	Pathfinding with other national and institutional infrastructure investments and the configuration of the BioCommons to integrate with approaches developed in the pathfinding.
Securing research gains by integrating genomic data with itself and other data types.	Development of data integration capabilities in the BioCommons, in cooperation with non 'omic data holders, applying scaled up BioCommons Cloud capacity.
Workforce Uptake	
The growth in the number of researchers with new bioinformatics requirements.	Provision of infrastructure, tools and services that support common techniques needed by many researchers across a range of domains (e.g. genome assembly, genome annotation, etc)
The ongoing upskilling of the bioscience workforce.	Expansion and strengthening of current national training and reskilling programmes.
Infrastructure Supply	
Access to sufficient digital infrastructure that is aligned to research practice in life science.	Incorporation of national and institutional digital infrastructures in scaling up BioCommons services that align with community requirements and expectations surrounding use.
The speed with which new and evolving techniques need to be made widely available.	Harmonising infrastructure used in BioScience research in Australia with infrastructure in the USA and Europe and the active involvement in global software stack developments.

Figure 4: Challenges prioritised through consultations to date, with planned BioCommons response

4.3 Characteristics

The implementation of the BioCommons will emphasise the following characteristics.

Start with National Intent

The BioCommons will be resourced and governed in the national interest. A related goal is to enrol founding participants that are also governed for national outcomes.

Invite Participation

A successful BioCommons will involve a significant commitment of resource, sourced from a large set of participants most of whom could not be expected to join immediately. Therefore the forms of participation and the corresponding participant characteristics and obligations will be defined at the service access level, the supply level, and at the governance level.

Partner Internationally

A global wave of investment is being made into life science related digital data and associated methods. The intention of the BioCommons is to 'ride that wave' and by doing so, to derive significant benefits to Australian life science related research.

Engage Communities

The BioCommons will build a national community of practice around each service it offers, that is strongly connected to international equivalents. The BioCommons governance model will ensure leadership from those sources does influence decision making.

Mature over time

The deployment of technology for research has inherent risks, and being a new technology, the impact of genomics is generating a tidal wave of change that comes with risks and rewards. The growing international commitment to the Galaxy platform, the development of federated global data archives such as LocalEGA and the existence and adoption of commercial services (in genomics in particular) are evidence of a growing maturity.

Enhance Coordination

Critical resources exist in the Digital Data and eResearch Platforms capabilities (AAF, AARNet, ARDC, NCI and Pawsey). Harnessing those resources to the benefit of the life sciences is a valuable but unexceptional ambition. Instead, the BioCommons aims to provide an outstanding means for achieving research impact into life sciences, for those capabilities.

Develop Stewardship

In the 'content' oriented layer of the BioCommons, a 'home' for service solutions is missing. A crucial role for participants will be their ability and willingness to host BioCommons services, in the interests of bioscience research, until an alternative approach to stewardship for the services is agreed.